

Functional Iterative Learning Control for Linear Systems

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Abstract—Many linear dynamic systems can usually be modeled in continuous time. However, to simplify the learning phase of Iterative Learning Control, the system output signal is frequently sampled, while the input is discretized, de-facto obtaining a discrete-time system. This work aims at preserving the continuous nature of the system, while tracking sampled outputs. To this end, we model the input signal as an element of a functional subspace, exploiting its infinite-dimension. Simulation results are presented.

I. INTRODUCTION

A classic approach to execute repetitive tasks is Iterative Learning Control (ILC) [1]. This strategy refines the control action to perform the desired motion closing the loop not in the time domain but in the iteration one. The application of ILC to continuous linear systems introduces the requirement of high order derivatives [2]. To avoid this issue, ILC is typically implemented on a discretized model of the system. However, this inevitably constrains the exploration space of the learning rule, because the input is limited to be piece-wise constant.

The approach we propose to avoid this drawback, is to choose the feedforward control input as an element of a functional subspace. A similar approach has already been considered in [3]–[5] to enhance the ILC extrapolation behavior. However, these works perform the functional expansion directly on the discrete system instead of an alternative to zero-order holding. Other approaches are terminal ILC (TILC) [6], [7] and Point-to-Point ILC (P2PILC) [8], [9], which still present piece-wise constant inputs, but sampled with higher frequency w.r.t. the output. Moreover, the input is updated relying only on the measurements of the tracking error at the samples of interest instead of its whole evolution. Moreover, these works do not exploit the oversampling of the input to learn inputs for systems with more outputs than inputs.

To summarize, in this work we propose a novel ILC framework for non-square linear systems, which learns a continuous control input in a functional space (Fig. 1). This solution allows to track sampled outputs without constraining the input to be piece-wise, and it allows to choose a functional space large enough to cope with systems with fewer inputs than outputs. Necessary and sufficient conditions for ILC convergence are presented.

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Fig. 1. Functional Iterative Learning Control scheme: u_j is the continuous input signal with iteration index j . The output y_j is sampled at o instants. We aim at having $y_j(T^1) \dots y_j(T^o)$ equal to the reference $\bar{y}^1 \dots \bar{y}^o$. The learning strategy is divided into two phases: i) u_j is modeled as a linear combination of iteration-independent basis functions $\pi_1 \dots \pi_{m_o}$; ii) the weights $\alpha_j^1 \dots \alpha_j^{m_o}$ are iteratively learnt through proportional error feedback.

II. FUNCTIONAL ITERATIVE LEARNING CONTROL

a) *Problem definition:* We refer to the model of a continuous time linear system

$$\dot{x}_j = Ax_j + Bu_j, \quad y_j = Cx_j, \quad (1)$$

with iteration index j , $A \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$, $B \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times l}$, $C \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times n}$, $x_j \in \mathbb{R}^n$, $u_j \in \mathbb{R}^l$, $y_j \in \mathbb{R}^m$, with the classic meaning. It should be noted that (1) is usually not square. We consider a finite set of time instants $\{T^1, \dots, T^o\}$; the superscript is an index, and $T^0 = 0$ is the starting time. The desired output values at the given times are defined as $\bar{y}^1 \dots \bar{y}^o \in \mathbb{R}^m$. The objective of this work is to design a learning law such that $u_j(t)$ leads to

$$\lim_{j \rightarrow \infty} y_j(T^k) = \bar{y}^k, \quad \forall k \in \{1 \dots o\}. \quad (2)$$

b) *Main Result:* We focus on the evolution of the input u_j . The key idea behind our framework is to make the ILC problem square by learning u_j in a large enough subspace of a functional space. Specifically, the space of all possible continuous functions is infinite-dimensional. We can parametrize a generic element of this space as follows

$$u_j(t) = \pi(t)\alpha_j, \quad \pi = [\pi^1 \dots \pi^o] \in \mathbb{R}^{l \times m_o}, \quad (3)$$

with $\pi^i(t) \in \mathbb{R}^{l \times m}$ and $\alpha_j \in \mathbb{R}^{m_o}$. This parametrization allows to achieve two objectives. First, the time-dependent and the iteration-dependent components of $u_j(t)$ that are separated. Second, instead of learning a generic u , we can simply find a learning rule for the vector α_j . Theorem 1 presents such a learning law and provides conditions for convergence.

Theorem 1. Consider the linear learning rule

$$\alpha_{j+1} = \alpha_j + L \begin{bmatrix} \bar{y}^1 - y_j(T^1) \\ \vdots \\ \bar{y}^o - y_j(T^o) \end{bmatrix}, \quad (4)$$

with $L \in \mathbb{R}^{m_o \times m_o}$. The combination of (3) and (4) fulfills (2)

Fig. 2. Tracking error evolutions across iterations.

with $x_j(0) = x_0$ for all j , if and only if

$$\rho(I - LH) < 1, \quad (5)$$

where ρ is the spectral radius of the argument, and

$$H = \begin{bmatrix} \int_0^{T^1} C e^{A(T^1 - \tau)} B \pi(\tau) d\tau & & \\ & \ddots & \\ \int_0^{T^o} C e^{A(T^o - \tau)} B \pi(\tau) d\tau & & \end{bmatrix} \in \mathbb{R}^{m_o \times m_o}. \quad (6)$$

Proof. Please refer to [10] for the proof. \square

At this point, to define the learning rule we need two choose two variables: the set of functions $\pi(t)$ and the learning gains L . The former can be freely chosen provided that H is non singular. This shifts the problem to finding L . Eq. (4) is formally equivalent to standard linear learning rules, and condition (5) is analogous to convergence conditions typically found in the literature [1]. As a result, classic ILC algorithms can be transferred into this framework with little modification.

III. SIMULATIONS

We validate the proposed framework on the challenging case of controlling all the $2N$ states of a system using only one input. The system under analysis is an interconnection of N masses ($m = 1$) constrained to a single direction of motion. These bodies are linked by linear springs $\kappa = 2$ and dampers $\beta = 1$, and they are actuated by a single force u_j applied at the last body. The system dynamics is not reported here for the sake of space, but it can be found in [10]. The output is the full stats, i.e., N positions and N velocities. We sample it three times T^1, T^2, T^3 , with $T^2 = 18$ s and $T^3 = 20$ s. We simulate an increasing number N of masses and $T^1 = 8$, and we simulate a fixed number of masses $N = 3$ and $T^1 \in \{2, 5, 8, 11, 14\}$. The desired outputs are $\bar{y}^1 = (1/N, 2/N, \dots, 1, 0, \dots, 0)$, $\bar{y}^2 = (0, \dots, 0, 0, \dots, 0)$, and $\bar{y}^3 = \bar{y}^2$. The base functions π are chosen as $6N$ Gaussians, with variance $T^3/(12N)$ and shifted in time such that they homogeneously cover the interval $[0, T^3]$. This choice leads to a full rank H for all the tested values, but it presents a condition number too large when $N > 5$. We set the learning gain as $L = (H^T H + S)^{-1} H^T$, with $S = 10^{-2} I$. Fig. 2 shows the evolution of the error over iterations. The error converges to values close to zero after few iteration in all the tests except for $T^1 = 2$ and $T^1 = 14$. This is due to the fact that the number of Gaussians being in their variance range is less than three in these two seconds spans. Fig. 3 shows the whole simulation

Fig. 3. Simulation at 10^{th} with $T^1 = 8$ and $N = 5$. Black crosses indicate the reference values.

with $T^1 = 8$ and $N = 5$. The reference is precisely tracked with a reasonable control input.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

This work presented the Functional ILC framework, which enables the learning of continuous inputs to regulate the output of a linear system at discrete instants. Future work will extend this method to industrial robots.

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